

Customer Perception and Socio-Cultural Dissimilarity in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: The perception of customers amidst multilingual/cultural/Religious diversities in Nigeria, has made it complex for marketing strategist to determine the exact behavioural pattern of the consumer; hence a rigorous process in organizational decision making. The purpose of this study is to examine the perception of customers and its socio-cultural dissimilarities in Nigeria. The issues to be addressed by this study includes; the effect of language in customer perception, the consummate effect of customer perception based on religious sentiments and the consequences of socio-cultural diversity on customer perception. The main concepts, models and theories of customer perception, micro-marketing and cultural dissimilarities will be examined. Specifically, this study adopted The Cognitive Dissonance Theory–The Belief Disconfirmation Paradigm. Descriptive research methodology was adopted using standard multiple regression model to analyse and test the hypothesis of the study based on the enunciated dimensions of customer perception which includes; language, religious sentiment and cultural diversities. The discussion of the study findings was based on the study objectives, theoretical/empirical gap and the outcome of the analysis. The study recommended the need for marketing strategists to acknowledge existing dissonance (culture, language and religion) in customer pre/post purchase behavioural perception, and fashion out engaging plan of action that could enhance effective implementation of product/service marketing in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: Customer Perception, Socio-Cultural, Language, Religion, Dissimilarity

INTRODUCTION

Customer perception connotes the ability of an individual to adapt his/her senses to proffer meaning to information received, transmitted and processed in the brain (the percept); via marketing stimuli on product /service offering, interpret and provide solution based on their unique socio-cultural, religious, psychographic and environmental circumstances. The effective adaptation of marketing mix in product service delivery must acknowledge the core basis of this signals that drives information through the sensory organs, resulting in the decision whether or not to patronize such product/service brand based on; experience, expectation and attention/action. (Soltani et al., 2019; Goldstein, 2015; & Goldstein, 2010). The perception model that fit into customer perception is the Sack and Gary perception which delineate perception into three categories; i) perceiver, - once a persons' stimulus is attracted to a particular based on inducements, feelings and encounters, ii) target – This is the item of perception which is based on available information about the focus and, iii) situation – the effect of environmental factors on the percept. (Alan & Gary, 2011) Culture is the way of life of the people living within a specified geographical location at a given period of time. Culture involves the behavior, custom, beliefs, norms, tradition and custom of the people. (Spencer-Oatey, 2012; & Tylor, 1871). Communities globally are shaped by certain norms that are acceptable or not acceptable within the society; this is openly expressed in the peoples' attitude, cooking, music, arts, craft, dressings, gender disparity, spoken language and mannerism (Chigbu, 2015). Nigeria is a heterogeneous and diversified cultural society made up of various ethnic nationalities; the nation became Nigeria through amalgamation of the Northern and Southern protectorates in 1914 by the British colonial administration. Nigerian language index in 2013, identified 452 different languages across the country, but the outstanding ethnic groupings in the country includes; Hausa/Fulani, Yoruba, Ibo, Efik/Ibibio, Ijaw. The diversity in languages lies the core basis of cultural diversification which is well ingrained in; desires, pursuits, interrelationships, perception expectation and power distance; these cues shape the entire facet of the people politically, socio-economically and on religious lines (Odejebi, 2014; Oyèníyí, 2012; Hofstede & Hoppe, 2004; & Hofstede, 1989).

In conceptualizing the study on customer perception, previous studies on this field were specifically examined within Nigeria and the result showed that; (Mathew et al., 2014; Arli, & Tjiptono, 2014; Odejebi, 2014; Hamdan et al., 2013). Examined the causal effect of religion on customer ethics, (Nwankwo et al., 2014). the authors examined the effect of customer value system on perception, Gladson, 2008), made a critical assessment on the strategy needed in attracting diversified customers, (Eshiett & Eshiett, 2021; & Fadipe 1970). The author explained the need to adapt a dynamic differentiation of product/services such as extravagant funeral spending in some Nigerian culture, and articulated on the need for marketing professionals to adapt to the funeral process

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in Yoruba culture as a means of appealing to customers within that region Adamolekun, 2001). In retrospect, previous studies examined is restricted to the attitudinal aspect of the customers, as well as assessment of their value system. This study is quite unique as it specifically examined the underlying effect of language as a unique aspect of determining the perception of customers in Nigeria; hence, the study becomes necessary in order to fill the existing literature gap.

Table 1. Previous Conceptualization on Customer Perception Dissimilarities

Study	Conceptualization	Item of Perception	Parameter of Measurement
(Mathew, Abdullah, binti., Ismail, binti M. 2014; Arli, & Tjiptono, 2014; Odejobi, 2014; Hamdan, Issa, Abu, & Jusoff, 2013).	Role of religion in customer ethics	Religious perception	Empirical Study; Causal effects
(Nwankwo, Hamelin, & Khaled, 2014).	Consumer value system	Customer Satisfaction	Empirical Study; Motivation of customers
(Gladson . 2008)	Market orientation	Business Strategy	Empirical Study; Business Performance
(Fadipe 1970).	Differentiation Technique	Business Ethics	Empirical Study; Sociology of the Yorubas
(Adamolekun, 2001)	Reasons for Extravagant funeral spending's	Motives	Empirical Study; Funerals

Statement of Problem

The essence of understudying the behavior of customers by marketing strategist is to afford marketing experts the opportunity to profile and target various groups of customers within a given geographical region. Once a target market has been identified, the marketer must differentiate the target market effectively; to enhance proper positioning that will serve all facet of the target market. The application of marketing mix by any expert could still face uphill task in the face of embedded socio-cultural, religious and language diversity; additional effort will be required in assuaging such customers based on the under-listed items;

A critical assessment of the society by Nigerian language index in 2013, it was ascertained that a minimum of about 452 different languages is spoken across the country, since language is one of the key factor in a multifarious society as ours, and is a key determinant in product/service decision, distribution of products, marketing communication decision; a proper awareness of these precepts could enhance an adequate understanding of the perception of customers; as well as appropriate application of the marketing mix across the country.

Religion has a vital role in assessing the behavioral pattern and belief system of the people, this involve the process of worshipping supernatural deities; which is believed by the worshipers to have control over the affairs of men. Hence, marketing strategist must guard against the any form of offensive/abusive attributions or usage of materials that could be offensive to customers' religious beliefs/sentiments, this could be nefarious to the perception of customers about such product/services.

The socio-cultural tenets of the customer in Nigeria is intertwined with the religious system of the people; This involves the way of life of the people living within a specified geographical location portraying similar; custom, beliefs, norms, tradition and custom. The essence understudying the cultural cues of the people by marketing strategists is to; enhance full understanding of what, how, why, when and in what form product services could be acceptable by the people. The main objective of this study is to evaluate the effect of customer perception on socio-cultural dissimilarity in Nigeria. additional objectives include; Evaluating the effect of language diversity on customer perception, to ascertain the effect of religious sentiment on customer perception, and to assess the effect of socio-cultural heterogeneity on customer perception in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Perception

The concept of perception involves active participation in activities within a given community enhances total participation of individual and groups in socio-cultural, economic, political spheres, and environmental sustainability (O'Faircheallaigh, 2010; UNECA, 2005). According to Rega and Baldizzone (2015), public participation as a nexus for mitigating conflict, disagreements, environmental crisis amongst communities (Nwafor, 2006); averting violent crisis/wars by enhancing fair-play and unhindered interaction amongst individual and groups. (Lawal et al., 2013). The purpose of enhancing free flow of interactions/communication amongst individual and groups is to enhance the overall development of the communities and the nation at large; hence the

need to effectively acknowledge culture, language and religion of the people to enhance openness, ease of intractability and proper management of conflicts. The ability to perceive appropriately individual and groups is the nexus of understanding how, what, which, why, when and where product services are needed by customers. (Esteves et al., 2012).

Theoretical Framework: Cognitive Dissonance Theory-The Belief Disconfirmation Paradigm

Cognitive Dissonance is one of the most dominant theory in social psychology, the theory was officially published by Leon Festinger in (1957), creating hundreds of studies in; deductions in attitudinal change, belief system, assimilation of morals, outcome of choices, inducements, emotions, consequences of disputation and perception amongst individuals/groups and the overall view of the ecosystem. (Harmon-Jones & Mills, 1999; Jones, 1985 & Festinger, 1957). The core basis of this theory is the resultant effect of decision made by individual and groups, the consequential effect of the belief system on consistent information flow and its effect on socio-cultural and behavioral tenets. For the purpose of this study, the sub- Cognitive Dissonance theory that underpins this study is the Belief-Disconfirmation Paradigm (Harmon-Jones; & Mills, 1999; Markus, & Kitayama, 1991; & Heine, & Lehman, 1997; Festinger et al., 1956).

The Belief-Disconfirmation Paradigm

The consequential effect of dissonance is observable whenever individual/group that had a certain form of belief are exposed to consistent information that is at odds with their belief, it could result in misconception or travesty of the information received, this could result in non-acceptance or rebuttal of the information; and working hard to persuade others within the group, and even extend to persuade non-group members of the belief system rejects such information. If there is any contradiction in the group belief system that is contrary to the expected outcome, otherwise known as disconfirmation, the group will ensure that it embark on an aggressive campaign to persuade; this will increase awareness that is in tune with the belief system. (Chen, & Risen, 2010; Harmon-Jones, 1999; Harmon-Jones; & Mills, 1999; Burris et al., 1997; & Festinger et al., 1956).

Fig 1: Customer Perception and Acceptability in a Cross-Cultural Process

The perception and acceptability of customer on cross-cultural basis, a similar experience in a multifaceted cultural society such as Nigeria is shown in Fig 1; in the context of this study, this shows how culture/language/religion could influence customers’ attitude towards acceptability/adaptability to a given product based on belief –disconfirmation paradigm across cultures. (Hofstede, 1999). Culture, language and religion are key indices in that determine consumers’ behavior/preference towards accepting or rejecting a particular product service offering advertised through social-media, that could be inimical to the health of youthful population (Albuquerque et al., 2019; Laaksonen et al., 2020; & Laaksonen et al., 2020); as well as influence social groupings based on their perception. (Gómez-Corona, & Valentin, 2019; Pellegrino et al., 2020).

Adapted; (2021). Sohyun Jeong Jeehyun Lee Effects of cultural background on consumer perception and acceptability of foods and drinks: a review of latest cross-cultural studies, 48, 248-256, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2021.07.004>

Familiarity is a key index in consumer buying decision and preferences, expectation, when customers are familiar with certain products, it increases the degree of its acceptability and publicity through Word of Mouth (WOM), familiarity enhances customers’ expectation and mitigates product/service rejection. (Jamir et al., 2020; Torrico et al., 2019; Nacef et al., 2019; Cecchini et al., 2019). Customer expectation has substantial influence in identifying what product/service the customer may prefer to purchase,

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Expectation is a complex cultural cue that has other associated factors such as; language, norms, values, dressing and overall behaviour of the product/service provider factors has outstanding impact on customer buying behaviour. (Li et al., 2020; Nacef et al., 2019)

The information available at the socio-cultural space on the belief system and social values of a specific product can increase acceptability or rejection of such product. On consumption of a particular product/service, the customer becomes the brand ambassador to either build the brand or destroy it, based on expectation and personal experience after consumption of the product. (Jamir et al., 2020; Torrico et al., 2019). Labels are also very marketing tool used in product differentiation, product label with high level of acceptability could promote itself, and drive patronage than its rival; the reverse is the case with product of low rate of acceptability. The effects of other contributing cultural factors such as; Language, Values, Demographics and Specific age group: children must be well regulated by government to ensure sustainable socio-cultural and environmental balance. (Li et al., 2020; Dando, 2019; & Nacef et al., 2019).

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive methodology was adopted for the study in which questionnaires were administered to respondents; as well as comprehensive interviews conducted to clarify areas in which the questionnaire could not cover effectively. The study design is based on the conceptual framework used in the process as a guide for; collecting, measuring and analysing of data, (Saunders et al., 2009). Convenience sampling technique was adopted; hence 383 respondents from the four major ethnic nationalities (Hausa, Yoruba, Ibo, Efik/Ibibio) were purposively selected as sample from the population at 0.95 level of confidence, to establish the relationship between customer perception and socio-cultural differences in Nigeria. The research instruments were subjected to reliability test to ascertain its level of consistency. The Cronbach alpha coefficient on customer perception, and the outcome was far higher than 0.65, which indicates that the research construct is reliable. (Nunnally, 1978)

A breakdown of the questionnaires that were collected revealed that; 333 questionnaires representing (87%) were returned and were validly used for the study, 31 respondents representing (8%) were not returned at all, while 19 respondents representing (5%) were rejected due to cancellation and mutilation by respondents,

Table 1; Respondents Rate Table

Questionnaires	Number of questionnaires	Percentage of questionnaires
Returned	333	87%
Rejected	19	5%
Not returned	31	8%
Total	383	100%

Analysis of Data

In analysing the data effectively, the study deployed the multiple regression model to ensure that the variables are statistically controlled, other reports analysed include; Multi-collinearity Diagnostics, as well as model summary, ANOVA and Coefficient were deployed in analysing each of the hypothesis as listed below:

Multi-collinearity is a process whereby two or more predictor variables in a multiple regression model are highly correlated, meaning that one can be linearly predicted from the others with a substantial degree of accuracy. In this situation the coefficient estimates of the multiple regression may change erratically in response to small changes in the model or the data. The outcome is shown on the coefficient table in the column labelled Tolerance and VIF (Variance Inflation factor) which is an inverse of the Tolerance value

Regression Analysis Results

Table 2: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	83.555	5.866		14.243	.000		
1 Culture	.522	.135	.194	3.871	.000	.948	1.055
Language	.117	.167	.035	.701	.484	.969	1.032
Religious Sentiment	.246	.125	.099	1.969	.050	.947	1.056

a. Predictor (Constant) Cultural Dissimilarity

b. Dependent Variable Customer Perception

Table 2; shows the regression model with the dependent variables (Culture, Language, and Religious sentiments), The column denoted by Beta indicates that the variables has been transmuted to the same scale for ease of comparison, (ignore all negative signs

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in the table). In this case the dependent variables that made their outstanding contribution in the model are, Culture .194, Religious Sentiments .099, and Language .035, Amongst all the variables, Culture made the highest contribution, while Language made the least contribution amongst all the variables in the model. The Standardized beta values shows the standard deviations in the dependent variable that could affect a unit change in the predictor, and since the value is less than .05, it indicates that it is making a unique contribution to the predictor in the equation. (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2001).

Test of Hypothesis 1: Language diversity have no significant effect on customer perception in Nigeria.

Table 3: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.297 ^a	.098	.076	10.06453	.088	7.406	1	368	.000	1.625

a. Predictor (Constant) Cultural Dissimilarity

b. Dependent Variable Customer Perception

The Model Summary table 3; refers to the entered variables which include; (Culture, Language and Religious sentiments 'a') while the dependent variable is denoted by; (Customer Perception denoted by 'b') The R Square values in the model summary table is .098 per cent, adjusted R Square is denoted by .076 percent. This connotes that customer dissimilarity has added same level of variance to customer perception in Nigeria. The level of significance is .000, this shows that the model is statistically significantly with, $p < .0005$).

Table 4: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1470.067	3	105.213	7.406	.000 ^b
	Residual	40747.889	368	110.295		
	Total	42217.956	382			

a. Predictor (Constant) Cultural Dissimilarity

b. Dependent Variable Customer Perception

The ANOVA table 4. is statistically significant with a significance of 0.000; Sig = .000, this really means $p < .0005$., which means that cultural dissimilarity –The independent variables (Culture, language and Religious sentiments) have significant effect on Customer perception. The significance of the factor implied in the study.

Test of Hypotheses 2: Religious sentiments have no effect on customer perception in Nigeria.

Table 5: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.605 ^a	.594	.738	10.26888	.071	6.480	1	368	.000	1.671

a. Predictor (Constant) Cultural Dissimilarity

b. Dependent Variable Customer Perception

The outcome of the analysis on table 5; shows that reliability has significant effect on Customer perception. The model of the equation is statistically significant with the value of 0.000 which is below the 0.05 alpha levels. It also shows that the effect of Religious sentiments on customer perception is high since computed R value of 0.605, R Square value of 0.594 and adjusted R ratio value of 0.738 are each greater than the standard limit of 0.4000. Therefore, the religious sentiment has significant effect on customer's perception in Nigeria.

Table 6: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1737.854	3	1537.854	6.480	.000 ^b
	Residual	30809.103	368	108.450		
	Total	42546.956	382			

a. Predictor (Constant) Cultural Dissimilarity

b. Dependent Variable Customer Perception

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Table 6; Examines the statistical significance of model shows that Sig = .000, which connotes that $p < .0005$. which means that the independent variable - Religious sentiments have significant effect on Customer perception. (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2001).

Test of Hypothesis 3: Socio-cultural heterogeneity have no significant effect on customer perception in Nigeria.

Table 7: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.548 ^a	.602	.705	10.47305	.502	.902	1	387	.343	1.628

a. Predictor (Constant) Cultural Dissimilarity

b. Dependent Variable Customer Perception

The results of the Regression analysis on table 7; shows that cultural heterogeneity 'a' has significant effect on Customer Perception denoted by 'b'. The R Square values in the model summary table is .602 per cent, adjusted R Square is denoted by .705 percent. This connotes that customer dissimilarity has added same level of variance to customer perception in Nigeria. The level of significance is .000, this shows that the model is statistically significantly with, $p < .0005$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The discussions on customer perception and socio-cultural dissonance in Nigeria. The prevailing effect of culture on the perception of the people is overwhelming, firms make frantic effort to customize their products in line with this observable differences. A case in point is Indomie Noodles that has differentiated its products to target all facets of existing dissimilarities.

Customer Perception: The language effect

The crave for liberalized trading across the country has been the dream of every administration, but language barriers, in a country with a minimum of over 452 languages, it becomes very necessary to acknowledge difference in ethnic languages as a tool for business growth. Nigeria is known to have the most diverse language ranges in Africa. The major languages are; Hausa, Yoruba, Efik/Ibibio, for the purpose of commerce, English is adopted as the official language, (NPC, 2012).

Language and culture is synonymous and must always be acknowledged such to enhance interrelationship between firm and their customers. (Grossberg, 2013).

Customer Perception: Religious diversity effect

The interrelationship between faith and interrelationship between individual and groups and how they perceive their environment. (Koenig, 2012). Religious values affect a lot of social behaviours such as; shopping habits, dressings, public discussions and perception. Nigeria is predominantly of Christian, Moslems and Traditional religious faith; hence the perception of each individual has a lot to do with their faith; this also affects customer purchase behaviour/loyalty (Eshiett & Eshiett, 2021), consumption pattern and interactions with others during periods of global uncertainties as experienced during the COVID pandemic (Eshiett & Eshiett, 2021a), uncertainties also that could affect global supply chain/product distribution (Eshiett et al., 2022a), religious influence on followers (Cleveland et al., 2013; & Swimberghe et al., 2009), of such diversities having racial discriminatory undertone (Meer, 2013), the religious inclined economic effect on product performance in the market (Chen & Hungerman, 2014), and sustainable attitudes of religious followers in waste management that conforms with the preservation of the ecosystem.

Customer Perception: The cultural Effects

Nigeria is a secular state with diverse Socio-cultural and ethnic settings, the perception of individual and groups is based on their ability to interact/integrate amongst each ethnic nationality and even globally. Mokhlis, (2009). The advances in technology through Information and communication Technology – ICT -through automated applications of Artificial Intelligence – AI and Robotics, researchers have suggested that culture is a psychological aspect of human behavior that could broaden societal perspective on new product management (Eshiett & Eshiett, 2022), on how reason and act with other global players around us such as integrating in the society on how to adapt technological innovations during periods of uncertainties; to achieve set societal objectives (Eshiett & Eshiett, 2021a), other authors see culture as not only helping our perception of the world; but also as increasing our reasonability between the universe and mediation. Hence, people respond positively or negatively based on how their culture/language is appreciated by the world around them. (Hofstede, 1989; & Grossberg, 2013).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The effect of socio-cultural diversity in the Nigerian concept is important in adapting learning to unravel how customer perspective of product/services could be enhanced. In developing economies such as Nigeria, socio-cultural cues must be well managed by marketing strategist in order help in developing product/services for the satisfaction of the customer.

Socio-cultural cues should also be seen as an opportunity to profile virgin markets, segment them appropriately, target each section of the market with appropriate marketing mix, and effectively position product/services; through appropriate differentiation for the purpose of providing goods and services at a profit to firms. Therefore, proper adaptation to socio-cultural cues, and the provision of quality services by firms to customers is a critical nexus in accomplishing this laudable project of economic revolution in Nigeria.

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